

DEVELOPMENT OF AGROSERVICE IN OUR REPUBLIC BASED ON MODERNIZATION.

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Abstract. *In the development of agroservices in the republic, there was a need to develop them on the basis of modernization and diversification. In this article, the main directions of the future development strategy of the development of agroservices on the basis of modernization are scientifically based.*

Keywords: *Agroservice; cluster; basics of clustering; modernization; diversification; development strategy; Modernization of service networks; digital agroservice; integration; hidden economy.*

РАЗВИТИЕ АГРОСЕРВИСА В НАШЕЙ РЕСПУБЛИКЕ НА ОСНОВЕ МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ.

Аннотация. *В развитии агросервисов в республике возникла необходимость их развития на основе модернизации и диверсификации. В данной статье научно обоснованы основные направления будущей стратегии развития агросервиса на основе модернизации.*

Ключевые слова: *Агросервис; кластер; основы кластеризации; модернизация; диверсификация; стратегия развития; Модернизация сервисных сетей; цифровой агросервис; интеграция; скрытая экономика.*

INTRODUCTION

Rapid development of the republic's agrarian sector and ensuring continuous development of the country's economy on this basis was determined according to the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" based on the Decree No. PF-60 approved by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev. As stated in this development strategy, "By ensuring stable growth rates in economic sectors, in the next five years, GDP per capita will be 1.6 times higher, and per capita income will increase to 4,000 US dollars by 2030, and create a foundation for entering the ranks of "higher-income countries"" identified as a priority task. The implementation of this process in the agrarian sector of the economy, especially in the organization of agroservice, requires systematic work.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Modernization is one of the most important driving forces in the rapid development of the republic's economy. The modernization process affects the social life of the country's population, initially changes the worldview of the population, creates a new demand for products and services. Also, the quality, form, type, methods and speed of the products produced in economic sectors will also change. Modernization refers to the use of innovative technologies for the production and service of new types of products by the employed population in economic sectors. Naturally, such changes will force people employed in economic sectors to change their profession or take up a new profession. As a result of such important structural changes occurring in economic sectors, the employed population will decrease in some sectors. And in some, the number of employed people will increase, between them there will be an atmosphere of intense competition, which is an important condition for development. Such changes in the country's economy, at first, create difficult problems in terms of ensuring the employment of the

population. In addition, the modernization process creates new jobs and has a positive effect on employment through the formation of new demands for products and services. It is not appropriate to develop strategic decisions about the modernization of the service sector without carefully studying these problems arising from modernization. between them, an atmosphere of fierce competition is created, which is an important condition for development. Such changes in the country's economy, at first, create difficult problems in terms of ensuring the employment of the population. In addition, the modernization process creates new jobs and has a positive effect on employment through the formation of new demands for products and services. It is not appropriate to develop strategic decisions about the modernization of the service sector without carefully studying these problems arising from modernization. between them, an atmosphere of fierce competition is created, which is an important condition for development. Such changes in the country's economy, at first, create difficult problems in terms of ensuring the employment of the population. In addition, the modernization process creates new jobs and has a positive effect on employment through the formation of new demands for products and services. It is not appropriate to develop strategic decisions about the modernization of the service sector without carefully studying these problems arising from modernization. the modernization process creates new jobs and has a positive effect on employment through the formation of new demands for products and services. It is not appropriate to develop strategic decisions about the modernization of the service sector without carefully studying these problems arising from modernization. the modernization process creates new jobs and has a positive effect on employment through the formation of new demands for products and services. It is not appropriate to develop strategic decisions about the modernization of the service sector without carefully studying these problems arising from modernization.

At the same time, an important task defined as a priority task in the "Strategy of Development" of New Uzbekistan is "Improving the system of providing agricultural services based on science and innovation." Supplying agro-industrial enterprises with raw materials and increasing the volume of production by 1.5 times"it is necessary to fulfill it as a main strategic task.

Regarding the implementation of the process of modernization in the republic's economy, it was noted that "Today, our country faces huge tasks in the sphere of state and society, according to its scale and scope. One of them is to ensure a more stable development of our economy, to diversify and modernize it, and to continue work on technical re-equipment of production.. It is necessary to emphasize that the modernization of industries and sectors is directly connected with the development of science. President Sh.M. Mirziyoev in his address to the Oliy Majlis on December 29, 2020 also stated that "science and innovations are the foundation of the country's development, without a doubt." that he explained.

RESULTS

There are scientific views and opinions of industry scientists and experts on the modernization and diversification of sectors and industries in the economy.

Economist A. Auzan, K. Kelimbetov "... in the conditions of globalization, the implementation of modernization works is not only important, but also a necessary condition for development in order to raise the relations between economic sectors to a new level"- they emphasized. Economist V. V. Inozemtseva believes that "if modernization raises labor productivity to the level of labor productivity in European countries, then new jobs will not be

created, on the contrary, the labor market will become unstable." I.A. Ashmarov "If economic sectors are modernized, social problems may arise in this sector. Therefore, modernization should create new jobs in economic sectors. Also, if modernization leads to job cuts in one sector, it creates new jobs in another sector. If modernization does not change the sectors of the economy and create new jobs, it is considered a illogical innovation states that.

It can also be seen in the work "The World economy: a millennial perspective" by economist A. Maddison. He said that in the modernization of the country's economy, the rate of growth of the share of GDP per capita is of great importance, as well as that it is extremely difficult to move to the modernization stage without social upheavals, only countries with a high and stable level of economic growth can pass it, the process of economic modernization is theoretically and practically rich. he very skillfully explained the experience and that it is considered a new era for the development of the country.

It should be noted separately that some theoretical aspects of the process of modernization of the country's economy have been analyzed in the works of Uzbek economists. In particular, economist E.Sh.Shodmonov's "The main directions of balanced and proportionate development of the economy in the process of modernization of the country" in his monograph, it is based on the fact that ensuring balance and proportionality is an important direction in the process of crisis prevention and achieving economic stability. Yu.Q. Yoldoshev's "Liberalization, modernization of the economy in Uzbekistan, raising the standard of living of the people: results and priorities" and in his monograph, comments were made about democratic renewal in the country's development. M.Q.Pardaev, T.Kh.Mamasoatov, O.M.Pardaev in their monograph entitled "Modernization, diversification and innovation-important factors of economic growth" stated that "... there are four types of modernization of the economy, i.e. modernization of means of production, showed the modernization of technological processes, the modernization of economic management methods, and the modernization of the qualifications and skills of employees". Economist U.A. Madrahimov's scientific article entitled "Fundamentals of Economic Modernization in Uzbekistan" divided the process of modernization into social and economic types. He included the modernization of agriculture, industry, small business and private entrepreneurship in the economic type of the modernization process, and the educational network of the service sector, the structural structure of the personnel training system in the social type, and showed the need to improve labor relations.

Due to the existence of conflicting opinions on the modernization of the country's economy, in many developing countries clear ways of modernization of sectors and sectors of the economy have not been developed. Only some countries have developed a strategy for the implementation of the modernization process. For example, the Russian Federation has developed a state program called "Strategy-2020" for the modernization of the country's economy, which includes: "social and economic development of the country, raising the standard of living of the population, gaining its place in the world economy in the 21st century, making the country's economy the first in international competition. to stand in line, as well as to ensure the national security of the country, to exercise the constitutional rights of citizens, and aimed at similar social and legal goals". Later developed "Innovatsionnaya Russia-2020" the state program called is also aimed at these goals. Reforms for the modernization of the country's economy are defined in these programs. However, ways to eliminate the social and economic problems that are inevitable due to modernization have not been developed.

Based on the above opinions of economists regarding the modernization of the economy, it can be said that the process of modernization of the service sector, firstly, increases the employment of the population, and secondly, it allows the effective use of the potential of each labor resource for the development of the country. Based on these, it can be concluded that the process of modernization of the service sector plays a major role in the development of the country, and therefore, at the same time, it is not free from social problems.

Modernization processes create two-way changes for the country's economic development.

DISCUSSION

On the one hand, modernization provides an increase in the volume of GDP, an increase in the income of the population, and an improvement in the standard of living of the population through the growth of labor productivity;

On the other hand, as a result of the introduction of new techniques and technologies and the corresponding increase in labor productivity, modernization causes a decrease in the number of employed people in the economic sectors and an aggravation of the employment problem.

Based on these two situations and the opinions of the above-mentioned economists, we believe that it is necessary to take a deeper look at the process of modernization in the service sector from the point of view of ensuring the employment of the population. In our opinion, if the modernization process is carried out step by step, based on a clear model and a certain procedure, it will lead to better results. This aspect of the modernization process is similar to the market mechanism. That is, if economic sectors are modernized, there will be serious changes in ensuring the employment of the population. This process in the life of the country, when it is managed with great difficulty and great intelligence, makes it possible to achieve noteworthy achievements in the way of the country's development.

The process of modernization of service sectors, especially agroservices, differs sharply from the process of modernization of agricultural and industrial sectors of the economy. For example, the modernization of agroservices increases the level of food supply to the country's population, creates abundance, preserves ecological balance, and increases the export potential of the sector. This process is also reflected in the creation of new types of service and increasing its speed. Modernization of the service sector plays an important role in increasing the volume of gross services and improving their quality. Modernization creates the following opportunities for the agroservice sector:

- creates new jobs by increasing the types of agroservices;
- agroservisdv creates the volume of services;
- improves the quality of agroservice;
- increases the speed of service in the agricultural sector;

As a result of the modernization of Agroservice, the labor productivity of the employees will increase and, accordingly, their real income will increase. At the same time, there will be a relative reduction in the number of employees employed in the sector, and as a result, the problem of employment and unemployment will become more acute.

CONCLUSION

In the research work, the conceptual development directions for the modernization of agroservices in the Republic in accordance with the "New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" were developed, and in our opinion, they are as follows:

First, the formation of the "Digital Agroservice" service system, which determines the systematic development of the agricultural sector in the Republic;

Secondly, the wide introduction of innovation in Agroservice, especially the development of cooperation relations between enterprises of the agro-industrial complex and scientific institutions, which create the possibility of applying modern technologies to the field, on the basis of integration;

Thirdly, systematic organization of increasing the special role (share) of agroservice in order to increase the weight of services in increasing the gross domestic product in the Republic;

Fourthly, strengthening the introduction of investments, especially foreign investments, which create the possibility of rapid development of agroservice as a "driver" sector of the economy in the Republic;

Fifth, to develop the agricultural service cluster in the Republic and deepen the integration of science and practice in the field on this basis;

Sixth, as an important opportunity in the Republic, to establish the implementation of agroservices in peasant (private) farms on the basis of modern mechanisms;

Seventh, to systematically establish the supply of modern personnel in accordance with the demand of agroservices in Uzbekistan;

Eighthly, based on the task of reducing the share of the "hidden economy" in the agricultural sector (reduction by 3 times, comment, defined in the State program), the most important conceptual directions, such as the implementation of systematic work in the sector, were defined.

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